

IPBES VA Chapter 3 - Systematic review on Method Families

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 3. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Ch. 3 that is to assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches for the integration of different types of values. For the chapter to be based on a broad review of valuation methodologies and approaches that have been applied in the different specialised sources of information, Chapter 3 did a first scan of a wide diversity of valuation methods and classified them into four method families, each family sharing similar fundamental properties. This report explains the systematic review for each of them to find literature that describes these method families.

Process overview:

Nature-based valuation methods

Statement-based valuation methods

Behaviour-based valuation methods

miro

Integrated valuation methods

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Protocol

Nature-based valuation Methods:

Nature-based valuation methods are methods that gather or analyse observations of (changes in) biophysical properties of nature. These include observations on species, ecosystem structure and processes, but also landscape, topography, soil, water and air, etc. To identify the main types of nature-based valuation methods, the main challenges, issues and knowledge gaps associated with them, two sets of literature searches were performed focusing on review papers mainly.

The first one was performed to identify four main method subgroups: modelling methods, mapping methods, direct measurement methods, and participatory approaches methods. While these four groups are partly overlapping (e.g., some mapping methods can be used by modelling methods), they were created to give a good picture of the diversity of methods available.

The second one was performed to identify specific challenges related to the subgroups “mapping”, “modelling”, and “participatory approaches”; for which we performed three additional reviews. No review could be performed for “direct measurement” as this is a broad group which does not easily correspond to a specific set of keywords.

Some additional seminal papers that were known by the authors of the section but that were not identified by the literature reviews described above were also used to enrich the discussion.

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review of nature-based valuation methods

Search languages: English & Chinese

Search engine: Scopus & Science Direct

Exact search date: September 12, 2020

Sample extracted (A1): (20+392)=412 papers

Fields extracted:

- Title
- Abstract
- Keywords

Search terms:

```
TS= ("biophysical"  
AND "valuation"  
AND "review") AND  
TS= ("biophysical"  
AND "assessment"  
AND "review")
```

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review on specific challenges related to “mapping”, “modelling”, and “participatory approaches”

Search languages: English & Chinese

Search engine: Scopus

Exact search date: September 12, 2020
Sample Size (A2): (75+84+5)=164 papers
Fields extracted:

- Title
- Abstract
- Keywords

Search terms:

```
TS=((“biophysical”  
AND (“mapping”  
OR “modelling”  
OR “participatory”)  
AND “assessment”))
```

Treatment applied (R1): All the selected papers were sorted for relevance by ordering them in decreasing number of citations and, where the sample allowed it, screened only the first 100 papers. Duplicates were excluded. Relevant papers were selected for further review.

Sample extracted for A and A1 (A): (13+(1+5+1))=20

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF1_(A).csv

Analysis of the data: Papers were fully reviewed to build the narrative contained in section 3.2.2.1 Nature-based valuation in Chapter 3 of the values assessment.

Statement-based valuation:

Value stating methods are a family of methods and approaches that directly ask people to express their values either verbally, in writing or through other actions solicited by the valuation process (e.g., ranking components of nature or indicating preferences) (Carson et al., 2018; Tinch et al., 2019). As such, the methods in this family generate information *directly from participants* of the diverse ways in which they perceive and value nature. To identify the main types of statement-based methods, the main challenges, issues and knowledge gaps associated with them one literature search was performed.

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review of statement-based valuation

Search languages: English

Search engine: ISI Web of Science

Exact search date: June 15th, 2020

Sample extracted (B1): 1917 papers

Fields extracted:

- Type of publication
- Title
- Abstract
- Authors
- Journal
- Publication Year
- Volume
- Issue

- DOI

Search terms:

```
TS= ("review"
AND "stated preference")
OR("contingent valuation")
OR ("Choice Experiment*")
OR("Ethnographic interview*")
OR("Narrative research")
OR ("Happiness survey*")
OR("Life Satisfaction approach*")
OR("Q-methodology")
OR("Expert elicitation*")
OR("Mental mapping")
OR("Public good game*")
OR("Deliberative valuation*")
OR("Nominal group technique*")
OR("Talking stick")
OR("Sharing circles")
OR("Photo-voice*")
OR("Delphi panel*")
OR("participatory scenario*")
OR("Participatory map*")
AND NOT("focus group*")
OR("questionnaire")
OR("interview*"))
```

Treatment applied (R2): On a first round of screening resulting papers were screened based on the following criteria i) if they were labelled as reviews; ii) excluding medicine-related disciplines; iii) whether (or not) they had a suitable title;

Sample extracted (B2): 191 papers

Location and Format of the Data (B1): IPBES_VA_3.3_Lit_Review_MF2_ (B1).xls

Treatment applied (R3): Abstracts from the Selected papers (B1) were classified as high/medium/low interest for describing general pros-cons, why, when and how to use or not use any method from the statement-based valuation family. Papers that only refer to one particular method (and not to stated preferences in general) are classified often as medium and only as **high** if they seem very relevant.

Sample size (B): 40+65+31 = 136 papers.

Location and Format of the Data (B2): IPBES_VA_3.3_Lit_Review_MF2_ (B2).xls

Analysis of the Data : Papers scored with high relevance were further reviewed through a qualitative analysis, and summarised in subsection 3.2.2.2. Overview of statement-based valuation methods.

Behaviour-based valuation

Behaviour-based methods quantify or qualify NCP revealed through observations of people's behaviour. This family of valuation methods includes both economic and non-economic methods. Two reviews were conducted to examine the literature on behaviour-based methods in two ways: a) a systematic search of relevant review articles; and b) a valuation method specific search of key literature for both value revealing economic (travel cost, hedonic pricing, production function, cost of illness, and replacement cost methods) and non-economic methods. In addition, a targeted search (c) was conducted for a specific

method to examine some common or thematic literature that was excluded from both approaches.

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review of behaviour-based valuation based on relevant review articles.

Search languages: English

Search engine: Scopus

Exact search date: June 15 2020

Sample extracted (C1): 258 papers

Fields extracted:

- Title
- Abstract
- Authors
- Journal
- Publication Year
- Keywords

Location and Format of the Data (C1): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_initial sample_(C1).csv

Search terms:

```
TS= ("valuation method")
OR ("economic valuation")
OR ("environmental valuation")
OR ("Revealed preference*")
OR ("hedonic pric*")
OR ("travel cost*")
AND ("biodiversity")
OR ("ecosystem service*")
OR ("nature*")
AND ("review*")
OR ("meta-analysis")
OR ("synthesis")
OR ("guideline*")
OR ("manual*")
AND NOT (SUBJAREA, "ENGI" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "BIOC" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "MEDI" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "VETE" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "NEUR" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "PHAR" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "CHEM" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "COMP" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "MATH" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "IMMU" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "PHYS" )
OR (SUBJAREA, "CENG" )
OR ( SUBJAREA, "MATE" ))
```

Treatment applied (R4): All selected papers were screened through a close examination of the abstracts, introductions and conclusions.

Sample extracted : 74 papers

Location and Format of the Data (C2): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_selected sample_(C2).csv

Treatment applied: Papers were read to examine the applications and the extent of strengths and weaknesses of specific methods discussed in each review article to integrate them in the description of the behaviour-based valuation methods family.

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review of behaviour-based valuation for both value revealing- economic and non-economic methods.

Search languages: English

Search engine: Scopus

Exact search date: June 15, 2020

Sample extracted (D1): 278 papers

Fields extracted:

- Title
- Abstract
- Authors
- Journal
- Publication Year
- Keywords
- DOI

Location and Format of the Data (D1): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_initial sample_(D1).csv

Search terms:

```
TS=((valuation
OR valuing)
AND("environmental valuation")
OR ("monetary valuation")
OR ("non-monetary valuation")
OR ("non-monetary valuation")
OR ("hedonic price method")
OR ("hedonic pricing approach")
OR ("travel cost method")
OR ("replacement cost method")
OR ("damage cost")
OR ("opportunity cost")
AND ("nature")
OR ("biodiversity")
OR ("ecosystem service*")
OR ("environment"))
AND NOT ((SUBJAREA,"ENGI" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"COMP" )
OR (SUBJAREA,"MATH" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"ENER" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"MEDI" )
OR (SUBJAREA,"BIOC" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"CENG" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"NEUR" )
OR (SUBJAREA,"PHYS" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"MATE" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"CHEM" )
OR (SUBJAREA,"PHAR" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"IMMU" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"NURS" )
OR (SUBJAREA,"VETE" )
OR ( SUBJAREA,"HEAL" ))
```

Treatment applied (R5): All selected papers were screened through a close examination of the abstracts, introductions and conclusions.

Sample extracted (D2): 61 papers

Location and Format of the Data (D2): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_selected sample_(D2).csv

Treatment applied: Papers were read to examine the applications and insights specific to one or more than one methods.

Type of analysis/search/review: Key literature examination for some methods.

Search languages: English

Search engine: Targeted search in Scopus

Exact search date: June 15, 2020

Sample extracted (E1): 37 papers

Fields extracted:

- Title
- Authors
- Journal
- Publication Year
- Pages

Location and Format of the Data (E2): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_sample_(E1).csv

Search terms: Method family 3 review was complemented by a targeted search and expert examination of key literature. It was done using either article title or author(s) or some other unique identifier specific to a particular behaviour-based method.

Treatment applied (R6): All selected papers were screened through a close examination of the abstracts, introductions and conclusions.

Sample extracted (E2): 33 papers

Location and Format of the Data (E2): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_sample_(E2).csv

Treatment applied: The 33 papers were read to integrate methodological aspects of valuing nature in the description of this method family.

Integrated valuation Methods:

Integration and bridging valuation methods tend to be viewed as a ‘process’ or ‘framework’ rather than a method type since they are often used to synthesise information or to structure the process of valuation (Gomez-Baggethun et al., 2014; Jacobs, S. et al., 2016; Pascual, U. et al., 2017). As a consequence, many methods from the method families 1-3 sections can be bridged or applied in an ‘integrated manner’, and thus potentially fit in this category. A systematic literature review was performed, related to 4 specific sets of methods specifically aimed at value integration, namely Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), Integrated Modelling and Deliberative Methods

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic review on integrated valuation methods

Search languages: English & Spanish

Search engine: Scopus

Exact search date: October 15th, 2020

Sample extracted (F1): (95+151+40+77+22+38+28+20+5+1+9+5)=491 papers

Fields extracted:

- Authors
- Title
- Publication Year
- Journal
- Issue number
- Pages

- URL
- DOI

Search terms:

```
TS= ( TITLE-ABS-KEY((((("multi criteria" AND "decision making")
OR("Cost benefit analysis" AND "valuation")
OR ("integrated modelling")
OR ("Participatory mapping")
OR ("Deliberative monetary valuation")
OR ("Story telling")
OR ("Participatory psychometrics")
OR ("Transcendental values")
OR ("consensus analysis")
OR (Focus groups)
OR ("Narrative methods")
OR ("group deliberation"))
AND (DOCTYPE(re)
AND PUBYEAR > 2010
AND SUBJAREA (ENVI)
```

Treatment applied: (R7) All the selected papers were sorted for relevance by ordering them in decreasing number of citations and, where the sample allowed it, screened only the first 100 papers. Duplicates were excluded.

Sample extracted (F2): (19+26+17+9+1+1+5+2+4+1+3+4)=92

Location and Format of the Data (F2): IPBES_VA_3.3_MF4_literature_review_(F2).csv

Analysis of the data: Selected literature was reviewed and presented in a narrative format in section "3.2.2.4 Integrated valuation" of Ch. 3 of the Values Assessment.

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF1_(A)	.xls	24 KB	Resulting selected papers from both reviews on Nature-based valuation methods: 20 papers.
B1	IPBES_VA_3.3_Lit_Review_MF2_(B1)	.csv	317 KB	Resulting selected papers from the Systematic review of statement-based valuation methods after applying R2 (191 papers).
B2	IPBES_VA_3.3_Lit_Review_MF2_(B2)	.csv	220 KB	Resulting selected papers from the Systematic review of statement-based valuation methods after applying R3 (136 papers).

C1	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_initial sample_(C1)	.csv	554 KB	Original sample obtained from the Systematic review of behaviour-based valuation based on relevant review articles presenting the initial sample: 258 papers.
C2	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_selected sample_(C2).csv	.csv	161 KB	Selected sample from the Systematic Review of behaviour-based valuation based on relevant review articles with the 74 selected papers.
D1	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_initial sample_(D1).csv	.csv	580 KB	Initial sample from the Systematic Review of behaviour-based valuation for both value revealing- economic and non-economic methods, with 278 papers.
D2	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_selected sample_(D2).csv	.csv	109 KB	Selected sample from the Systematic Review of behaviour-based valuation for both value revealing- economic and non-economic methods, with 61 selected papers.
E1	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_sample_(E1).csv	.csv	8 KB	Selected sample from the key literature examination on behaviour based valuation methods with 37 papers.
E2	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF3_sample_(E1).csv	.csv	7 KB	Selected sample from the key literature examination on behaviour based valuation methods with 33 papers.

F2	IPBES_VA_3.3_MF4_literature_review_(F2).csv	.csv	47 KB	Selected sample from the Systematic review on integrated valuation methods, with 92 papers
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